

Reviewing 10 Generative AI Tools for Research as of Fall 2024

Christian J. Tai Udovicic, SOEST Postdoctoral Researcher, University Of Hawai'i At Manoa

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Generative AI Literature Review Tools

Summary

From the tools assessed, there were clear benefits to having AI-assisted literature reviews, but also clear limitations and the relevant literature suggested was often far from comprehensive. Note that findings are based on capabilities as of Fall 2024 and rapid developments in generative AI technology and the fine-tuned offerings by each of these services are likely to change over time (e.g., several updates for each service were released over the short period of assessment causing it to be challenging to offer a comprehensive and fair benchmark for each tool without constantly reevaluating rapidly updated functionality).

Recommendations (as of Fall 2024)

- In-depth literature reviews: Scite
- Overview of a body of literature: Consensus, Epsilon or Elicit
- Summarization and extracting key points / figures: Genei

Tips for using AI tools for research:

- Use natural language prompts: All of these AI tools are based on Large Language Models (LLMs) which are trained to understand natural language. Try to ask clear and specific questions as you would to a peer or student. This approach is different from how you may be accustomed to querying a search engine like Google (ex. Prompt: "What do pure anorthosite deposits tell us about early magmatic evolution of the Moon?" vs. Google search: "pure anorthosite deposits moon")
- Ask follow-up questions: LLMs generally have some "memory" of previous queries from the current chat session. Feel free to ask for more detail on a certain aspect or to clarify

some details that were missed in the original prompt - no need to repeat the full question.

- Start a new session: Sometimes the LLM memory can cause it to fixate on some detail raised earlier in the session and no amount of correcting it will pull out the info you intended. Feel free to start a new chat session where you can try a variation on your original query, but with a clean slate.

Genei

Genei is a service that allows you to upload papers and uses genAI to generate quick summaries, a list of figures and key points, and optional more detailed summaries of each section of a paper. The main goal seems to be to facilitate more efficient literature search - if you have already compiled a big database of papers and don't know where to find the most relevant info, you can quickly skim summaries and key points before deciding which papers to read more in-depth.

Link: <https://app.genei.io/>

Pros:

- Pulls out figures into a quickly scrollable sidebar that you can use to jump to that figure and its description in the paper. Useful if you remember a plot and want to find it again quickly
- Low chance of AI hallucination, in general "translating" text is one of the major strengths of AI at this point, so translating long form text into a short form summary will pull real information from the text

Cons:

- Chance of missing information, hard to know what the AI will pick up on in the paper and papers with many key points or nuanced stories might be oversimplified in the summaries
- Was the least polished of the tools and had the least functionality - was targeted only at the paper summaries rather than the literature search (helps deal with a large number of papers after they have all been found and downloaded)

Elicit

Elicit is an AI literature search tool that allows you to ask a plain language research question and summarizes the top 4-8 most relevant articles to answer the question (although the criteria for selecting the top papers is unclear). It allows users to customize different categories of “snapshots” about the paper, like “Abstract summary”, “Main findings” or “Limitations”, producing a table of short AI-generated summaries for those 8 papers for quick comparison. While useful for obtaining a broad overview of the literature, it was not suitable for in-depth research due to its limited depth and tendency to present information without sufficient explanation. It could be useful for early undergraduate work or a first introduction to a new field, but the result is far from comprehensive and is not a robust or in-depth literature review tool.

Link: <https://elicit.com/>

Pros:

- Fast and easy to use for converting a plain language question into a few real and relevant citations from the literature.

- Zotero reference manager integration for keeping track of saved papers that can be organized as a “library”. Related research questions can be organized into “Notebooks”.

Cons:

- Limited depth: Limiting research to 4-8 top papers can severely restrict the breadth of literature it is drawing from and therefore bias the “answers” to the posed questions to the results of a narrow subset of papers chosen by an opaque algorithm
- Repeat questions in a similar domain to test if it would turn up other important or contrasting literature about a topic often showing the same or similar top 4/8 papers. Could misrepresent the literature by showing only a tightly curated subset

Scite

Scite is an AI literature search tool that creates a network graph of citations and provides a quick summary of *how* a particular paper was cited. It adds a badge to references indicating how many citations of a paper were supporting, contrasting, or neutral mentions. The idea is to show which papers have had results supported by later literature and which have been more controversial. Scite provides information about its search strategy and the references it consulted which made it more transparent than other tools compared here. It integrates with Zotero and ORCID, offers a browser extension for easy access, and can generate easily navigable visual networks of citations.

Link: <https://scite.ai/>

Pros:

- Allows plain language questions and provides an answer with citations to back it up, which can then be saved to a collection or explored as a network graph of the literature

- The idea to rank supporting a contrasting citations with AI is interesting and could help flag more supported or more controversial papers in the field
- The transparency of the search strategy built confidence in its veracity and it appeared to make a relatively thorough graph of related papers in the domains tested

Cons:

- In practice, the vast majority of all citations were flagged as neutral “mentions” rather than supporting / contrasting, which could indicate that the tool is not accurately flagging more complicated concepts with support or dissent (i.e. it is probably just looking for phrases similar to “X agrees with previous work by Y”) or just too few papers in my field make value statements about other literature to make this feature useful. At best, this feature can be ignored, at worst, it risks making some papers appear more attractive to cite due to being more supported or more controversial if the user does not click through to see the nature of the support or disagreement
- Has a slightly steeper learning curve to get integrations setup and to really make use of its deeper functionality

Epsilon-AI

Epsilon-ai is a literature search tool that generates answers to plain language questions and provides supporting references. It is a user-friendly tool that could be a helpful starting point for research. It provides links to full articles and integrates with Zotero for reference management. However, when tested on different but related questions, it tended to cite a limited number of sources and did not always directly answer the posed question. It sometimes produced repetitive or circular arguments, likely due to limited source diversity.

Link: <https://www.epsilon-ai.com/search>

Pros:

- Clean interface and easy to use. Could be good for finding a few major papers related to a question as a starting point for an undergrad-level literature review. It then allows you to quickly see the paper's References and Cited By and you could then examine those for a more robust view of the literature.
- Shows exactly where an AI-cited concept came from in an article, so you can quickly hop to the relevant section of the article to verify the information or get more context.

Cons:

- Limited by preference for a small subset of articles, leading to repetitive and not entirely accurate answers to posed questions due to it pulling info from the same sources it deemed relevant
- Lacked depth to give confidence in the results being an accurate or robust view of the literature

Consensus

Consensus is an AI tool designed to answer plain language research questions by finding and summarizing relevant articles. It provides more nuanced answers than other tools evaluated here and generates potentially helpful tags of articles like "Highly cited" or the style of paper ("Literature Review", "Meta Analysis" or "Longitudinal study", etc). The eponymous "Consensus Meter" provides a visual summary of the answer to the research question by ranking papers that say Yes / Possibly / Mixed / No (i.e., if the posed question is a yes/no style question). While it may suffer from the same narrow scope of the literature that could introduce

bias, the AI generated summaries appeared to be more logical and appropriately referenced than results from the other two similar tools assessed here (Epsilon and Elicit).

Link: <https://consensus.app/>

Pros:

- Very clean and easy to navigate user interface. Clicking on a reference provides a snapshot of the study with some useful key points, details of the study (sample size, data used, study type, etc). It's also easy to hop from article to article by the referenced by and cited by links. This tool can be used to quickly gain more depth of understanding of the literature whereas other tools assessed here focused on top level breadth.
- Provides a list of related questions that could spur deeper thought about a topic, a little bit like a conversation with a colleague with real-time literature searches and well-referenced answers as feedback.

Cons:

- Unclear how the most relevant papers are selected and could open the tool to similar narrow-look biases as the others
- Potential con: study type and parameters appear more useful for biomedical fields where randomized controlled trials or meta-analyses are more common. These labels were less applicable for earth and space science style papers.

Generative AI Tools

Summary

Generative AI tools are rapidly undergoing massive increases in capacity since OpenAI released chatGPT in November 2022 based on the GPT3.5 model. In two short years, the underlying model has undergone 3-4 major upgrades (GPT-4, GPT-4o, o1, and the soon-to-be-released o3), each time vastly increasing the model's breadth of knowledge, comprehension of input "prompts", and ability to reason for increasingly complex tasks. OpenAI is not alone; models of similar capabilities have kept pace with chatGPT from competitors like Alphabet (Google), Meta, Microsoft, Anthropic, Perplexity, as well as fully open source models shared and iterated on by enthusiasts on the sharing platform, HuggingFace, or released by companies like NVIDIA and DeepSeek. With so many choices and the rapid improvement and release cycle, making any meaningful comparisons of these models was challenging and likely to be outdated as soon as the tests were performed.

Recommendations:

- Writing: Gemini, but ChatGPT, Claude and Perplexity had similar results.
- Coding: Claude or ChatGPT produced the most reliably correct and well-formatted code.
- Image generation: Claude produced the best technical figure, ChatGPT or Gemini can produce more creative artistic images and might be more useful for posters, talks, etc.

For these comparisons, I familiarized myself with each of the following 5 tools by applying them in my day-to-day research to gauge their utility, likelihood of "hallucination" (generating false information), and ability to comprehend, respond to and generate technical scientific prose.

Then I prompted each with the same following prompts and recorded the outputs below. These tests are far from exhaustive and not as comprehensive as they could have been if time allowed, but they provide a snapshot of model functionality as of Fall 2024 which may be useful to those reading soon or a curiosity for readers in the future who may have far superior tools widely available.

Prompts:

- **Proposal writing prompt:** Help me write a proposal to NASA. My hypothesis is that space weathering on the Moon has gradually slowed in the last billion years due to the lower flux of impactors. I would like to use imagery from multiple satellites to study how fast the lunar surface space weathers and to show that the recent weathering rate is slower than it was earlier in lunar history. Please write a short (<250 words) proposal abstract that concisely describes the problem, methodology, and hypothesis in technical but jargon-free language.
- **Technical drawing prompt:** Create an image of an impact crater in a side profile, labelling important features of the crater like the floor, rim, and ejecta blanket. The image should be clear and engaging enough to appear in a peer-reviewed journal article.
- **Coding assistance:** I prompted each tool for help on day-to-day coding tasks. The prompts were diverse in scope and complexity depending on the task of the day which made it hard to objectively compare the tools (and many independent benchmarks have been published for each tool that are much more comprehensive than my narrow and biased exploration). However, after 3 months of exploration, I found that the more reliable and useful tool was Anthropic's Claude, with OpenAI's ChatGPT in close second. The pro version of both tools allows for several hundred to thousand line

modules to be uploaded as context for a task. They could provide boilerplate code for analyzing and plotting data when given an example file in a commonly used format like CSV. For niche tasks like geographic mapping and analysis, the LLMs were limited in usefulness without prior knowledge of specific packages to use or previous code to build on. Simple data analysis tasks and producing code for plots provided much more reliable results. Coding with an AI assistant was an iterative process that often required multiple prompts to get to code that worked and produced the desired result. Although models are rapidly improving in capabilities, I would suggest that they are most useful as an assistant to scientists who already have some competence in reading, writing, and running code. Careful specification of prompts was important to receiving correct and useful code, while less experienced users may be intimidated by the amount of debugging and iteration required to run a script - or worse, trust a buggy script that successfully ran but did not do the intended task.

OpenAI ChatGPT

Link: <https://chatgpt.com/>

Proposal writing (abstract): The proposal abstract generated by ChatGPT was reasonable, and I could see it being a real abstract for a NASA proposal. ChatGPT doesn't currently cite its sources but I could see stock text being a useful starting point for a proposal, with specific details specified and citations added.

"Space weathering, driven by micrometeorite impacts and solar wind, alters the lunar surface over time, affecting its optical and physical properties. While the Moon's weathering processes are well-documented, the hypothesis that space weathering rates have slowed over the last billion years due to a reduced flux of impactors remains untested. Understanding this trend is critical

for interpreting the Moon's surface history and refining models of solar system evolution. This study proposes to use high-resolution imagery from multiple lunar orbiters, including data from the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO) and Chandrayaan-2, to quantify space weathering rates across surfaces of different ages. By analyzing spectral characteristics, regolith maturity, and crater density, we will compare weathering rates in ancient terrains (>1 billion years old) with more recent surfaces. Advanced image processing and machine learning algorithms will be employed to detect subtle differences in weathering signatures, correlating them with estimated surface ages. The findings aim to confirm that space weathering has decelerated over the Moon's geological history, providing new insights into the evolving dynamics of impactor flux in the inner solar system. This work will contribute to our understanding of planetary surface processes and inform future lunar exploration, including site selection for resource utilization and human missions."

Technical drawing: Generated using the openAI DALL-E, the result is cartoonish and text labels have typos and are not accurately describing the picture. Crater shape is inaccurate and the result is not a side profile view as requested. At present, this image generator seems more suited to artistic rather than technical images.

Microsoft CoPilot

Link: <https://copilot.microsoft.com/>

Proposal writing (abstract): The proposal abstract generated was more elementary than ChatGPT's, with the writing appearing more appropriate for an undergraduate or graduate level research project. The writing style and reasoning shown (linkage between ideas) was pretty simplistic.

Space weathering, driven by micrometeorite impacts and solar wind interactions, plays a critical role in altering the Moon's surface properties. My hypothesis is that the rate of space weathering has significantly decreased over the past billion years, correlating with a reduction in the flux of impactors. To test this hypothesis, I propose an analysis of high-resolution imagery from multiple lunar satellites, including the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO) and previous missions like Clementine and Chandrayaan-1.

By employing advanced image processing techniques and comparative analysis, I aim to quantify the extent and rate of space weathering across different lunar regions and time periods. Specifically, I will focus on identifying and characterizing surface features, such as craters and regolith changes, that serve as indicators of weathering processes. This study will involve a combination of spectral analysis and morphological assessments to draw a comprehensive timeline of space weathering rates.

The expected outcome of this research is to provide robust evidence that the recent rate of space weathering on the Moon is

Google Gemini

Link: <https://gemini.google.com/>

Proposal writing (abstract): The output proposal abstract was concise, detailed, and motivated the project well while providing reasonable and specific tasks that were not stated in the prompt but would be reasonable for this work. The writing style was technical but comprehensible and overall was the most impressive result for this task.

Space weathering, driven by micrometeoroid impacts and solar wind bombardment, alters the optical and physical properties of airless bodies like the Moon. This proposal investigates the hypothesis that the rate of lunar space weathering has decreased over the past billion years due to a declining impactor flux. We will analyze high-resolution imagery from multiple lunar missions, including the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO), Clementine, and Kaguya, to quantify the maturity of lunar surface features. Specifically, we will measure the spectral reflectance and color variations of fresh craters and their ejecta blankets of varying ages. By comparing the spectral changes associated with weathering across different crater populations, we will establish a timeline of weathering rates. This analysis will focus on craters with well-determined ages derived from crater counting and other chronometric techniques. This comparative approach will allow us to directly assess whether the rate of space weathering in recent lunar history is demonstrably slower

than that observed in older terrains, providing crucial constraints on the evolution of the lunar surface environment and the history of the inner solar system's impactor population.

Technical drawing: Uses the Imagen 3 image generation model which produced a similarly inaccurate image as the DALL-E 3 results with incoherent text labels.

Anthropic Claude

Link: <https://claude.ai/>

Proposal writing (abstract): Similar to Gemini, this abstract was concise, well-reasoned and provided actionable tasks that could accomplish the proposed project beyond the details given in the prompt. In general this abstract was high quality and reasonable but some choppiness in the order and flow of ideas makes it a close second to Gemini and a similar level to ChatGPT.

Space weathering - the darkening and reddening of lunar surface materials due to micrometeorite impacts and solar wind exposure - is a fundamental process that has modified the Moon's appearance over billions of years. However, the rate of space weathering may not have remained constant over lunar history. This project hypothesizes that space weathering rates have decreased significantly over the past billion years, primarily due to the declining flux of impactors after the Late Heavy Bombardment.

To test this hypothesis, we propose analyzing high-resolution imagery from multiple lunar orbital missions, including Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter, SELENE, and Chandrayaan-1. By comparing spectral properties of crater rays and ejecta of different ages across mare regions, we can construct a timeline of how quickly fresh material weathers to match the surrounding terrain. Our methodology combines automated crater detection algorithms with spectral analysis tools to measure weathering signatures in thousands of craters ranging from recent to ancient. These

measurements will allow us to model weathering rates through time. Preliminary analysis suggests younger craters weather more slowly than older ones, even accounting for age uncertainty. If confirmed, this finding would improve our understanding of lunar surface evolution and help calibrate crater-based age dating methods. The results would also provide insights into the changing micrometeoroid environment of the inner solar system over geological timescales.

Technical drawing: Claude is the only model to take a unique approach to the technical image task. It generated html code that drew the individual components of the diagram as vector lines and returned a .svg image. The result was a technical drawing in side-profile as requested with coherent text labels. The drawing also included reasonable and potentially useful additions not asked for directly in the prompt, like the original ground surface and scale bar.

Some label clutter made things hard to read, but this was easily fixed with a follow-up request “move the ejecta blanket label to the other side for clarity” resulting in the second image below, which is clear, in the style that was requested in the prompt, and given as editable svg code.

Perplexity

Link: <https://www.perplexity.ai/>

Proposal writing (abstract): This proposal abstract was well written and incorporated significantly more information than was included in the prompt to back up claims and provide a reasonable plan to approaching the proposed project. The Perplexity feature of providing citations and links to sources it used for information from the internet is very useful for technical writing and is unique among the current chatbot offering assessed here. However, somewhat ironically, some of the statements made in the abstract were factually incorrect, e.g., “solar energetic particle radiation” should probably be solar wind (SEPs are a thing, but it’s far from accepted that they are the only/primary source of solar space weathering), and “multi-temporal” is probably not the correct descriptor for the data in the way they’re being used to sense different geologic epochs rather than days to years between observations. These are both minor hallucinations that would likely appear in text generated by the other models if used for larger writing tasks, but these subtle mistakes are the most insidious and underscore the importance of having a careful and trained eye to verify any information generated by these LLMs.

Space weathering on the Moon's surface is a complex process driven primarily by micrometeoroid impacts and solar energetic particle radiation. This proposal aims to investigate the hypothesis that lunar space weathering has gradually slowed over the past billion years due to a decreased flux of impactors.

We propose to utilize multi-temporal imagery from various lunar satellites, including the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter Camera (LROC) and Moon Mineralogy Mapper (M3), to quantify the rate of

space weathering across different regions of the lunar surface. By analyzing spectral changes in the ultraviolet, visible, and near-infrared wavelengths, we can track the development of nanophase iron particles, which are key indicators of space weathering[1][4].

Our methodology involves:

1. Identifying and mapping fresh craters of various ages using crater counting techniques.
2. Analyzing spectral properties of crater ejecta and rays to determine weathering rates.
3. Comparing weathering rates of craters from different geological epochs.
4. Correlating observed weathering rates with estimated impactor flux models.

We hypothesize that younger craters will exhibit slower weathering rates compared to older craters, reflecting a decrease in the micrometeoroid flux over time. This research will provide crucial insights into the long-term evolution of the lunar surface and improve our understanding of crater age dating techniques. Additionally, it will contribute to refining models

of the impact flux history in the inner Solar System, with implications for planetary protection and future lunar exploration.

Citations:

- [1] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Space_weathering
- [2] <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/20230016899>
- [3] <https://www.purdue.edu/research/features/stories/bright-streaks-on-moon-product-of-space-weathering/>
- [4] <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8051153/>
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- [8] <https://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/images/39769/fresh-craters-on-the-moon-and-earth>
- [9] <https://www.pnas.org/doi/10.1073/pnas.0401565101>

Technical drawing: Perplexity was not capable of generating an image, but it instead described the important aspects of a crater in text and returned links to several web pages providing

figures exactly like the one requested. While not technically what was requested, this result was definitely more useful than the inaccurate attempts made by some of the other models.

Sources

Impact Craters | Astronomy - Lumen Learning

courses.lu...

Impact Crater with Ejecta Blanket -...

jpl.nasa

[PDF] Appendix F: Schematic Diagrams of...

ipi.usra

Show all

Simple Crater

Complex Crater

△ Breccia ▬ Fractured bedrock
 ■ Impact melt ▬ Central peak uplift
 □ Impact ejecta

Answer

I apologize, but I am not able to create, generate, edit, manipulate or produce images. I can only perceive and analyze existing images. I cannot create an image of an impact crater as requested. However, I can describe what such an image might look like based on the information provided in the search results:

A side profile image of an impact crater would typically show:

1. A bowl-shaped depression with a flat floor 1 4
2. An elevated rim rising above both the crater floor and surrounding terrain 1 4
3. An ejecta blanket surrounding the rim, consisting of debris thrown out by the impact 1 4
4. Possibly a central peak in the middle of the crater floor 1 3
5. Terraces along the inner walls of the crater formed by landslides 1 4

The image would be labeled to clearly identify these key features. The ejecta blanket would appear as a rough, hilly region extending outward from the crater rim 1. The overall shape would resemble a shallow "V" with the rim forming the highest points on either side 5.

Search Videos +

PRO Generate Image +

Conclusion

As AI tools rapidly become more capable and ubiquitous, it is worthwhile to stay apprised of current capabilities in the research and academia space, both to understand if they can be of use to your work but also to understand where issues in work from colleagues, students, and peer-reviewed submissions might arise. At the time of writing, AI capability appears to still be rapidly improving, with most of the tools assessed gaining major upgrades over the course of the 3 months taken to assess them. The major takeaways from this work can be summarized into three pieces of advice: be specific, be skeptical, and iterate.

Be specific: The first rule of all modeling, including in the training of AI models, is “garbage in, garbage out”. This also applied to prompts to any of the AI tools mentioned. While LLMs have become surprisingly good at understanding human language and adding helpful context from their massive training database, the work of science is often specific, technical, and precise. By prompting AI with precise language, results are more likely to be tailored to a specific need, or the limitations of the model will become glaringly apparent.

Be skeptical: The most frequent concern and complaint about using AI tools is their tendency to “hallucinate”, inventing false outputs that appear to satisfy a prompt. While the AI tools are getting better at refusing to answer rather than hallucinate a false answer, there is still some way to go, particularly at the edges of the model’s broad knowledge base (like a particular subdomain of science). However, a healthy dose of skepticism can allow these tools to remain useful and it is important to not trust their every output. Verifying any and all writing with a critical eye and testing all code extensively before relying on its outputs are second-nature activities for most scientists and that healthy skepticism can convert error-prone AI-generated outputs into useful text or code products.

Iterate: Nearly all useful AI outcomes required several iterations of prompts to fix mistakes, clarify what was originally meant, and/or improve the response. Much like editing

papers or debugging code, working with AI is an iterative process and is rarely perfect on the first try. There is a bit of a learning curve to knowing when to point out mistakes and have the AI retry a query vs. when to start a new chat instance if it is getting too hung up on an unimportant detail in memory vs. when to give up and take an alternative (perhaps non-AI) approach to a task. But just as you iterate on prompts, learning to use AI effectively is an iterative process that will only begin if a user is willing to try, be willing to fail, and to not immediately give up hope when obstacles arise.

In summary, these tools are most useful for tasks that can be quickly and accurately described in plain language (the prompt) and where the output is long or repetitive but easily verified (e.g. long boilerplate code for importing a file, editing values, and plotting some rows - and the correctness is immediately visible on the plot). However, if writing the prompt precisely (and perhaps iterating 2-3 times) takes the same amount of time as just doing the task (e.g. a jargony piece of writing or domain-specific code), then it might be best to just do the work. AI chatbots can also be useful in a variety of ways not investigated here, for example in the idea generation process to simulate a dialogue with a colleague, or perhaps to assist in managing or prioritizing tasks. These tools are extremely flexible and maximizing their utility requires some amount of experience with them, creative thinking, and willingness to experiment. AI, like all things in science, should be approached with intellectual curiosity and a healthy degree of skepticism, but have already and will continue to facilitate scientific advances going forward.

Final Thoughts

This work didn't allow a deep exploration of the ethics, geopolitical, and climate implications of using generative AI tools. The choice to use or boycott AI can be a personal and political one. I don't necessarily recommend anyone use, buy, support, or boycott generative AI, but now that it is out and widely available, I don't think we will be able to put it back in the box. Therefore, as responsible scientists and citizens, I think there is some civic duty to pay attention to the tools that exist, work with them enough to understand how they may be (ab)used and try to stay informed about the frequent leaps in capability. Only then will we be able to enact sensible policies around AI, demand forward-thinking laws and governance of the technology, and ensure ourselves and communities are safe from the potential social and climate risks associated with its widespread development and use. To become responsible stewards of the power of any new technologies, and our planet, it is important to understand them, and the people who interact with them. Thanks for reading this far. Welcome to the generative AI era.